

LEGAL REGULATION OF MEDIATION IN FOREIGN COUNTRIES: (USA, UK, AUSTRALIA)

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Annotation: *This article presents the history and reasons for the emergence and development of the institute of mediation in foreign countries, as well as the features of the legal regulation of the institute of mediation in these countries.*

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Modern mediation in the form in which it currently exists began to develop in the second half of the 20th century in the Anglo-Saxon system of law (USA, Great Britain, Australia).

There are several prerequisites for the emergence of mediation. The first is related to the formation of a new form of conflict due to the rapid development of the US economy, which consisted in a confrontation between trade union organizations and employers over working conditions and wages. Fearing a massive escalation in strikes, layoffs and massive plant closures across the country, the government has given the Department of Labor the role of a neutral mediator to resolve labor disputes. In 1947, a special federal body was created - the US Federal Service for Mediation and Conciliation Procedures, which is still in force today. A practical basis was laid for the development of the institution of mediation in the field of labor relations.

In the late 1960s, Neighborhood Justice Centers and Community Mediation emerged. The idea of their creation was the need to provide affordable legal assistance to persons who do not have the financial ability to seek protection in a state court. This was the second prerequisite for the emergence of mediation, which this time began to penetrate into the field of family law and the field of social security.

The third prerequisite, closely related in meaning to the previous ones, was the negative side of the civil process, concerning the issue of costs. Incurring costs for both parties was inevitable and did not depend on the outcome of the case, and in economic disputes they reached enormous proportions. Plus, the process itself was too long. As a result, the parties willingly agreed to a settlement agreement, and turning to alternative dispute resolution (hereinafter - ADR) became more and more attractive.

In 1972, the first professional organization of mediators was created in the United States. By the end of the 1980s, a specialized training system was formed, aimed at training qualified personnel for conflict resolution. Then, since 1988, a

similar experience began to be used in the educational system of Australia, closer to 1990 - in the universities of Canada and the UK.

In 1990, the United States carried out a reform of the civil justice system. In addition to the development of mediation as an out-of-court form of dispute resolution, it has actively begun to integrate into the state judicial system. By the end of 1995, more than 200 of the largest American corporations and more than 250 legal entities entered into an agreement that prescribed not to go to court until an attempt was made to reconcile in the event of a dispute.

In 2001, the United States passed the Uniform Mediation Act, which harmonized many laws issued in individual states. It is dedicated to establishing guarantees and limits on the confidentiality of information disclosed by the parties during the mediation. In the United States, a mediator is approached in 75-85% of cases of conflict situations, while agreements reached during mediation are implemented in 90-95% of cases.

In the UK, there is an Advisory Service for Conciliation and Arbitration (Acas Codes of Practice), the purpose of which is to promote the development of industrial relations and offer, at the request of the conflicting parties, assistance in resolving the dispute.

There is a special hotline where you can call to describe the conflict, preferences regarding the mediator, for which a list of specialists who meet the specified parameters will be offered. If no agreement is reached between the parties, the dispute is referred to the Labor Tribunal.

Mediation is also regulated by family law. The UK Family Law Act 1996 provides for the duty of a solicitor to refer persons seeking legal assistance in a family dispute to a mediator who has a state accreditation.

The Guidelines for the Royal Service of the United Kingdom establish the obligation of the claimant to contact the family mediator before filing a claim with the court, who is also charged with informing the claimant about the content and possibilities of family mediation and other methods of alternative dispute resolution.

In the People's Republic of China (hereinafter referred to as PRC), the idea of peaceful settlement of disputes occupies a central position. It is the only state whose constitution expressly provides for the creation of people's conciliation commissions that resolve disputes among the population.

There is a special law on mediation, in accordance with the provisions of which popular mediation is a process in which people's conciliation commissions convince interested parties of the need to reach a conciliation agreement on the basis of equal negotiations and good will, which will resolve the dispute that has arisen between them.

In the People's Republic of China, the basic law that directly regulates the mediation procedure is the Law on Mediation and Arbitration of Labor Disputes. The

main purpose of establishing the ADR in China is to reduce the burden on the judiciary.

Mediation acts as one of the mandatory stages of consideration of a labor dispute before litigation. If the number of participants in the dispute exceeds 10 people, then it becomes possible to choose one representative to participate in the mediation procedure.

Upon reaching an agreement on the result of mediation, a mediation agreement must be drawn up, which is binding on its participants. The parties are given a 15-day period to fulfill their obligations: if any of the parties fails to fulfill the obligation, the other party has the right to apply to the arbitration court. By the way, the procedure itself is completely free.

In Japan, mediation is one of the most popular types of ADR. It is regulated by a special Law on Civil Application, and is also contained in the norms of industry legislation. It is defined as the settlement of a conflict with the help of a neutral person (mediator) who helps the parties to work out their own solution.

There are two types of mediation: carried out in civil courts and carried out in family courts. In family courts, when considering disputes, its application is mandatory.

Reconciliation can be carried out both at the initiative of the court and at the request of the parties themselves at any stage of the trial, and also, notably, after a court decision has been made. In the arbitration court, the judge may, on his own initiative, order mediation without the consent of the parties, but only at the initial stage of the trial, and then only with the consent of the parties.

If mediation is carried out after the initiation of legal proceedings, then a conciliation commission is created, consisting of a judge and two mediators.

In some cases, the judge may act as a conciliator alone, and in his absence, these functions may be assigned to a court employee who has the appropriate training. All costs of the procedure are borne by the parties.

Thus, the rapid development of mediation was, first of all, in the countries of Anglo-Saxon law - the USA, Great Britain, Australia, and then began to be effectively applied in Europe. Mediation is quite common in Asian countries and neighboring countries.